

Structural Optimization of Tubular Steel Wind Turbine Towers with Respect to Buckling

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Abstract

As attention on wind energy is progressively increased, wind turbine towers grow in height and the blades become longer in order to better exploit the available wind potential. As a result, actions on the towers are also increased and their safe and cost-effective design is important for the further development of the wind energy sector. A commonly used type of wind turbine tower is the tubular steel tower which offers several structural advantages and has dominated the market over other alternatives, such as truss-type towers. The tubular wind turbine tower is composed of a number of cylindrical and/or conical shells, manufactured in the factory and erected on site by means of bolted ring flange connections. In the present article, the buckling design of an actual 120m tall wind turbine tower is described, aiming towards optimizing the tower with respect to weight, hence also cost, and taking properly into account restrictions pertaining to fabrication, transportation and erection. Among several constraints that the tower design has to satisfy, in the present paper only buckling is addressed, based on Eurocode 3 recommendations for steel shells, as well as on nonlinear finite element analyses, and taking into account realistic action effects in normal and extreme conditions. Namely, initial results obtained by verifications according to EN1993-1-6 are then compared to numerical results from non-linear finite element analysis accounting for geometrical and material nonlinearity and imperfections (GNMNA). Thus, areas where the tower wall thickness has margins for reduction are identified, so that in future work an optimized tower design can be achieved.

Keywords: wind turbine towers, tubular steel towers, stress design, buckling analysis, non-linear analysis, imperfection analysis

1. Introduction

For the purpose of the present research, an actual wind turbine is used with a tower of approximately 120m height. The wind turbine tower consists of five cylindrical parts and one conical part at the top, which are transported to site and are erected and bolted together on site with preloaded bolts. The lower five parts have a constant outer diameter equal to $D_{ext}=4300\text{mm}$, which is the largest size that can be transported by truck, while their thickness varies along the height of the tower from $t=60\text{mm}$ to $t=16.5\text{mm}$ from base to top. The upper part of the wind turbine tower has a conical shape, with external diameter varying from $D_{ext}=4300\text{mm}$ to $D_{ext}=3685\text{mm}$ from bottom to top, while the thickness of the sixth part remains constant and equal to $t=15\text{mm}$.

The material of the tower shell is steel of grade S355 with nominal yield stress equal to $f_y=355\text{MPa}$ and $f_y=335\text{MPa}$ for tower shell thickness smaller or equal to $t=40\text{mm}$ and larger than $t=40\text{mm}$

respectively. Corresponding nominal values of ultimate stress are $f_u=510\text{MPa}$ and $f_u=470\text{MPa}$, while elasticity modulus is equal to $E=210\text{GPa}$.

The design of the wind turbine tower is performed according to EN1993, Part 1-6, “Strength and stability of shell structures”, EN1993-1-6:2007 [1]. The fabrication quality class for the wind turbine tower is considered equal to B; however, the effect of fabrication quality class will be also investigated and presented.

2. Verification of the tower according to EN1993-1-6

The verification of the wind turbine tower is performed at characteristic points along its height for the corresponding design forces taking into account realistic action effects in normal and extreme conditions, as obtained by means of aeroelastic simulations, in which the tower has been modeled with beam elements of equivalent cross-sections. Each set of design effects taken into account consists of a maximum design force/moment and its corresponding design forces/moments. Checks according to EN1993-1-6 [1] have been performed by means of analytical calculations and spreadsheets that have been developed for that purpose.

The ultimate limit states to be considered for the design of steel shells are:

- LS1: Plastic failure limit state
- LS2: Cyclic plasticity

As in our case, cycles of loading and unloading do not produce yielding in tension nor in compression, this limit state is not applicable.

- LS3: Buckling

Buckling limit state is checked for all actions causing compressive normal and shear stresses on the tower shell. As a result, the tower is checked against meridional (axial) buckling, circumferential (hoop) buckling and shear buckling.

- LS4: Fatigue

The limit state of fatigue is the condition in which repeated cycles of increasing and decreasing stress lead to the development of a fatigue crack. Fatigue is not considered in the present paper.

2.1. LS1 check – Plastic limit verification

For the verification of this limit state, the design stresses shall satisfy the condition

$$\sigma_{\text{eq,Ed}} \leq f_{\text{eq,Rd}} \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{eq,Ed}}$ is the equivalent design stress and $f_{\text{eq,Rd}}$ is the von Mises design strength. Analytical description of the plastic limit state can be found in EN1993-1-6 [1].

2.2. LS3 check – Buckling verification

For the verification of this limit state, the design stresses shall satisfy the following conditions,

- for meridional (axial) buckling

$$\sigma_{\text{x,Ed}} \leq \sigma_{\text{x,Rd}} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{x,Rd}}$ is the axial buckling resistance of tower shell

- for hoop (circumferential) buckling

$$\sigma_{\theta,Ed} \leq \sigma_{\theta,Rd} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{\theta,Rd}$ is the circumferential buckling resistance of tower shell

- for shear buckling

$$\tau_{x\theta,Ed} \leq \tau_{x\theta,Rd} \quad (4)$$

where $\tau_{x\theta,Rd}$ is the shear buckling resistance of tower shell

- for the combined buckling check of meridional, hoop and shear buckling

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{x,Ed}}{\sigma_{x,Rd}}\right)^{k_x} - k_i \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{x,Ed}}{\sigma_{x,Rd}}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{\theta,Ed}}{\sigma_{\theta,Rd}}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\theta,Ed}}{\sigma_{\theta,Rd}}\right)^{k_\theta} + \left(\frac{\tau_{x\theta,Ed}}{\tau_{x\theta,Rd}}\right)^{k_\tau} \leq 1.0 \quad (5)$$

Analytical description of the buckling limit state can be found in EN1993-1-6 [1].

For the buckling verification it is assumed that the critical buckling length corresponding to each tower cross-section is equal to the length of the corresponding part, e.g. it is the length between two ring flanges. Moreover, depending on each part's length, its diameter and its thickness, the part is categorized as long, medium or short cylinder. In our case, all parts are categorized as long cylinders. Finally, it is important to clarify the boundary conditions of each part. EN1993-1-6 [1] distinguishes between three boundary conditions, BC1 (clamped), BC2 (pinned) and BC3 (free). For the base of the tower boundary conditions are assumed to be BC1, while at the ring flanges boundary conditions are assumed to be BC2.

2.3. Verification results of analytical checks

In Figure 1, all exploitation ratios along the height of the tower for all characteristic positions of the tower derived from equations (1) to (5) are illustrated. The horizontal axis of the diagram represents the exploitation ratios while the vertical axis of the diagram represents the height of the tower. Fabrication quality class for the verification of the tower is considered equal to B.

Figure 1: Exploitation ratios along the height of the tower for plastic limit and buckling verifications

In general, buckling is more adverse than plastic limit state, as expected given the height of the tower. The meridional buckling check is dominant over the height of the tower, with the exception of the upper 20m, where torsion-induced shear buckling governs. The maximum exploitation ratio is obtained from the meridional buckling check at a height of approximately 63m and is equal to 0.913 (<1.0).

2.4. Effect of fabrication quality class

EN1993-1-6 [1] distinguishes between three fabrication classes, A (excellent), B (high) and C (normal). For better fabrication class the amplitude of imperfections to be used for buckling checks is smaller. Therefore, the capacity ratios of buckling checks (LS3) depend on fabrication class, while capacity ratios of plastic limit checks (LS1) are independent of fabrication class. In Figure 2, the exploitation ratios illustrated along the height of the tower are derived from meridional buckling state, as it is the most onerous state, and for all fabrication quality classes.

Figure 2: Exploitation ratios along the height of the tower for meridional buckling verification and for all fabrication quality classes

As expected, for better fabrication class, the exploitation ratios are lower. For worse fabrication class, the maximum exploitation ratios occur at higher positions over the tower.

3. Wind turbine tower numerical model

In order to employ a reliable and computationally effective numerical model for the tower analysis, several models with different types and meshing of finite elements were investigated. The ideal numerical model of the tower would be to model all the parts with 3d solid finite elements. However, this would result in a heavy model that would be very difficult to handle. For this purpose, three models were investigated: (a) The pylon shell is modeled with shell elements and the ring flanges with beam elements representing the section of both flanges acting together, taking into account the geometrical eccentricity between flange axis and shell mid-surface by means of rigid elements. (b) Both the pylon shell and the ring flanges are modeled with shell elements with the shell elements representing the section of both flanges acting together, (i) considering that the tower shell extends up to the mid-surface between the two flanges, and (ii) taking into account the tower shell trim due to the flange thickness by means of rigid elements. (c) Both the pylon shell and the ring flanges are modeled with 3d solid elements. For the investigation, linearized buckling analysis is performed.

The different models have been compared for the case of two cylindrical shells of 5m height with external diameter equal to $D_{ext}=4300\text{mm}$ and a uniform thickness equal to $t=50\text{mm}$, which are connected together via two ring flanges with width equal to $b=270\text{mm}$ and thickness equal to $t_f=140\text{mm}$ each. The lower shell is fixed at its base, while the upper shell is free at its top, with a rigid node where loads are applied. The thickness of the shell near the flanges is reduced to $t=38\text{mm}$, in order to direct buckling failure there.

Initially linearized buckling analyses are performed for the different models. In Figure 3 the critical load factors of models (a), (b-i), (b-ii) are compared with the load factor of model (c), and a

satisfactory convergence is observed. In order to extend this conclusion, geometrically and material nonlinear imperfection analyses are also performed for the three simpler models (a), (b-i), (b-ii), using a more accurate geometry, being part of the actual structure, taking now into account the variable thickness of the tower and a larger in height segment in order to intensify the effect of geometric non-linearity. Initially, linearized buckling analysis is performed in order to obtain the first critical buckling modes (Figure 4). The first buckling mode is then used as shape of geometrical imperfection for the nonlinear analysis, while the size of the imperfection is calculated according to EN1993-1-6 [1] for fabrication quality class A.

In Figure 5 the stress distributions obtained from GMNIA at the ultimate point of the analysis are illustrated. Comparing the load factors, a satisfactory convergence is also achieved. As a result derived from both linearized buckling analysis and GMNIA, model (a) with the pylon shell modeled with shell elements and the ring flanges with beam elements taking into account the geometrical eccentricity with rigid elements can be used for the verification of the wind turbine tower.

Figure 3: 1st buckling modes and critical load factors of (a), (b-i), (b-ii), (c) models

Figure 4: 1st buckling modes and critical load factors of (a), (b-i), (b-ii), (c) models

Figure 5: GMNIA stress distributions at the ultimate point of the analysis of (a), (b-i), (b-ii) models

4. Wind turbine tower verification with finite element analysis

The wind turbine tower verification is now also performed via nonlinear finite analysis with geometrical and material imperfections (GMNIA), employing model (a) of paragraph 3, namely modeling the tower with shell elements and the ring flanges with beam elements. In order to assess the buckling potential at different locations over the tower, successive models of parts of the tower below each flange are analyzed. Each model is loaded with the corresponding design forces/moments at its upper flange. GMNIA is performed taking into account an initial geometrical imperfection with the most unfavorable shape of the five primary buckling modes, determining the size according to EN1993-1-6 [1] and the assumed fabrication quality class. The size of imperfection is calculated for all three fabrication quality classes, A, B and C and the corresponding GMNI analyses are performed.

Due to size restrictions, the results of the GMNIA of only one part of the wind turbine tower are presented. Similar analyses and checks have been performed for all parts. The part of the tower chosen to illustrate the results is the fourth from the bottom, approximately between levels +46m and +65m. The cylindrical shell has a uniform external diameter equal to $D_{ext}=4300\text{mm}$, while its thickness varies along its height from $t=33\text{mm}$ to $t=25\text{mm}$ from base to top. Design forces are imposed on the model at the ring flanges at level +65m. The 1st buckling mode, used as shape of the initial imperfections is illustrated in Figure 6, and their size calculated according to EN1993-1-6 [1] is illustrated in Table 1 for the three different fabrication quality classes.

Table 1: Imperfection size according to fabrication quality class and ultimate load factors

fabrication quality class	gauge of length l_{gx} (m)	thickness t (mm)	imperfection size $\Delta_{w,eq}$ (mm)	$r_{R,GMNIA}$
A	0.43	24.5	6.1	1.221
B	0.43	24.5	9.8	1.101
C	0.43	24.5	15.3	1.010

Figure 6: 1st buckling mode of tower part

In Figure 7, the equilibrium paths of the examined tower part are illustrated for the three fabrication quality classes, A, B and C, while the ultimate load factors, from which the exploitation ratios resulted, are also presented in Table 1. The horizontal axis of the equilibrium paths corresponds to the horizontal displacement of the top of the tower part and the vertical axis corresponds to the load

factor. Part of the deformed shape of the tower and the corresponding effective stresses at the ultimate point are illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Equilibrium paths of examined tower part for fabrication quality classes A, B and C

Figure 8: Deformed shape and effective stresses of examined tower part at the ultimate point

Figure 9: GMNIA exploitation ratios of entire tower for fabrication quality classes A, B and C

The verification procedure described above was applied to all tower parts with their corresponding geometry, design forces and imperfections. The results of this procedure are illustrated in Figure 9 by means of exploitation ratios along the height of the tower. As expected, for worse fabrication quality class, the exploitation ratios are higher and closer to failure. For the wind turbine tower investigated in this project, the most onerous results from the analyses are approximately at 60m height. It should be

noted that in case of fabrication quality class B, the exploitation ratio is 1.0, which means that the tower is marginally safe, while in case of fabrication quality class C, the exploitation ratio is 1.1, indicating buckling failure.

5. Comparison of analytical and numerical results and discussion

The comparison between the analytical and numerical verification of the wind turbine tower is illustrated in Figure 10. For the analytical results, an exploitation ratio envelope is presented encompassing the plastic limit state as well as the buckling state, meridional, hoop, shear buckling and their combination, for fabrication quality class B. The presented numerical results are those derived from the process described in section 4, also for fabrication quality class B.

Figure 10: Maximum exploitation ratios of analytical and numerical verifications

In general, analytical and numerical results are in good agreement, apart from the middle of the tower where the numerical exploitation factor is larger than the corresponding analytical exploitation factor.

It is also observed that in lower and upper parts of the tower smaller exploitation ratios are observed, thus identifying the potential of shell thickness reduction and optimization with respect to buckling. This potential will be explored in future work, considering also the effects on fatigue checks and on avoiding tower resonance with the turbine's 1P and 3P rotation frequencies.

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